

Impact of Check Dams on Groundwater Recharge and Quality in Upper Vaigai Sub-Basin, Tamil Nadu, India

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ABSTRACT

Groundwater is essential for various sectors, including agriculture, domestic use, and industry. This study aims to assess the suitability of groundwater for different uses and understand the impact of check dams on groundwater quality in the Upper Vaigai Sub-basin in Theni district, Tamil Nadu, India. The water quality parameters analyzed included potential of hydrogen, total dissolved solids, electrical conductivity, major cations (calcium, magnesium, sodium, and potassium, and anions such as chloride, sulphate, carbonate, bicarbonate, and fluoride ion) to evaluate irrigation suitability. The groundwater quality before and after the construction of check dams at Mayiladumparai, Ambasamudram and Amachiyapuram was evaluated using electrical conductivity, sodium adsorption ratio, sodium percentage, and ion concentrations through Wilcox, United States Salinity Laboratory, and Piper plots. Results from these plots indicated that groundwater quality improved post-construction, making it suitable for irrigation. Groundwater within 5 km of the check dams was found to be suitable for drinking purposes. Additionally, the impact of the check dams on groundwater levels was analyzed using the Mann-Kendall, Sen Slope Estimator, and Innovative Trend Analysis methods. The results of this study reveal that in Ambasamudram, Mayiladumparai, and Amachiyapuram, the groundwater recharge rates increased by 47%, 44%, and 23%, respectively. Check dam construction has also improved groundwater quality and recharge, though the effectiveness varies based on site-specific factors such as geology, cropping patterns, and irrigation practices.

Keywords: *Agricultural Water Use; Aquifer Response; Hydrochemical Assessment; Non-Parametric Trend Methods; Recharge Structures, Seasonal Variability.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Water is a fundamental component of the natural world, significantly influencing the viability of organisms and the socio-economic advancement of communities. Natural water resources serve humans as sources of potable drinking water and irrigation (da Silva *et al.*, 2020). The accessibility and quality of water have shaped daily life, but

rapid population growth and agro-industrial expansion have increasingly challenged the maintenance of suitable water quality for diverse uses (Sinha Ray and Elango, 2019). Human, industrial, and agricultural activities pose serious threats to the ecological diversity of water resources. Numerous studies worldwide have analyzed groundwater quality using diverse methodologies.

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For instance, groundwater near the Rooppur Nuclear Power Plant in Bangladesh was assessed through 17 hydrogeochemical indicators from nine samples to determine drinking and irrigation suitability (Uddin *et al.*, 2023). In northern Karnataka, India, water samples from 68 wells collected quarterly (2013–2014) were analyzed for electrical conductivity (EC), pH, and dominant ions (Thirumurugan *et al.*, 2018). In Sheikhpura district, 195 groundwater samples mostly met WHO guidelines except for arsenic, which exceeded the recommended 10 µg/L limit for drinking water (Rehman *et al.*, 2023).

Groundwater quality in Nyamira County, Kenya, was evaluated through samples from three springs during the November 2018 rainy season (Rehman *et al.*, 2023). The Upper Yellow River region in China showed groundwater quality influenced by rock dominance, evaporation, and cation exchange, with nitrogen and fluorine as major pollutants. Although 96.19% of samples were deemed good via Integrated Weight Matter-Element Extension Analysis, 57% posed unacceptable health risks to children, and 21% to adults (Wang *et al.*, 2022). In India's Tamsa River basin, groundwater exhibited higher major ion and silica concentrations than river water, which had greater alkalinity. Both were suitable for consumption, household use, and irrigation, with variations linked to rock weathering, ion interactions, and human activities (Siraj *et al.*, 2023). In Ilesha West, Nigeria, groundwater quality for irrigation was assessed by physicochemical properties and heavy metals, including sodium adsorption ratio (SAR). Sodium (Na⁺), potassium (K⁺), calcium (Ca²⁺), bicarbonate (HCO₃⁻), carbonate (CO₃²⁻), and chloride (Cl⁻) were dominant ions. The Irrigation Water Quality Index (IWQI) indicated many wells fell under high-to-severe irrigation restrictions. GIS-based zoning in Abu Dhabi highlighted limited irrigation-suitable areas, emphasizing the need for real-time monitoring and risk

management to support sustainable agriculture (Siraj *et al.*, 2023). In the Jinghe River Basin, China, groundwater quality categories reflected human impacts, with unsuitable quality mainly in the north. Health risk assessments showed elevated carcinogenic arsenic risks, especially for children (Li *et al.*, 2022).

Heavy metal contamination in surface water of Jamalpur Sadar, Bangladesh, posed significant health risks, while groundwater quality indices and pollution categorizations confirmed unsuitability for consumption (Yakovlev *et al.*, 2023). Groundwater quality for drinking in South Korea was modelled using a neural network with 95% predictive accuracy, supported by 2D spatial analysis, indicating the necessity for revised management policies (Ahn *et al.*, 2023). Groundwater quality assessment in Dayrout, Upper Egypt, using indices and diagrams, revealed seasonal fluctuations in borehole water levels (Gabr *et al.*, 2021). Long-term analyses have highlighted contrasting groundwater trends across regions. Mann–Kendall tests in Terengganu, Malaysia, indicated rising groundwater levels from 2000 to 2012 under a tropical monsoon climate (Shaharudin *et al.*, 2021). Declining trends were projected for Uttar Pradesh and Karnal district, India, through modified Mann–Kendall and Sen's slope estimators, extending to 2050 (Kumar *et al.*, 2018; Zakwan, 2021). Groundwater levels near agricultural lands in West Bengal declined according to Mann–Kendall and Standard Groundwater Level Index analyses (Halder *et al.*, 2020). Ardabil Plain, Iran, experienced declines linked to human activity, prompting calls for additional hydrogeochemical studies (Daneshvar Vousoughi *et al.*, 2013). Sagar district, Madhya Pradesh, showed cyclical yet declining patterns identified through Kendall and regression tests (Thakur and Thomas, 2011).

Global case studies reveal further depletion concerns. Groundwater development in

Vietnam's Red River Delta from 1995 to 2009 was unsustainable in urban zones, with falling confined aquifer levels (Thakur and Thomas, 2011). The UAE, particularly Sharjah, experienced severe depletion and salinization over the past 15 years due to limited rainfall and population growth (Yilmaz *et al.*, 2020). Expanding reliance on groundwater in areas lacking surface water, combined with over-extraction, has accelerated depletion rates worldwide (Sinha Ray and Elango, 2019). Artificial recharge interventions have been implemented to address overuse. Check dams, small low-level structures built across rivers, streams, or channels, slow water flow, trap sediments, and create upstream reservoirs for irrigation, livestock, domestic supply, and aquifer recharge (Rao *et al.*, 2022). They also reduce sediment transport to downstream areas (Parimala Renganayaki and Elango, 2014).

The Upper Vaigai Sub-basin study in Theni aimed to assess groundwater suitability for agricultural, domestic, and industrial use through parameters such as pH, TDS, EC, and ion concentrations. It also aimed to evaluate the influence of multiple check dams (Mayiladumparai, Ambasamudram, Amachiyapuram) on groundwater quality using Wilcox, USSL, and Piper Trilinear plots; and analyze recharge trends within a 5 km radius using Mann-Kendall, Sen's Slope Estimator, and Innovative Trend Analysis. Findings confirmed the role of check dams in enhancing groundwater availability for irrigation and drinking purposes, contributing to sustainable water resource management.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Study Area

The Upper Vaigai sub-basin, situated in the Theni district of Tamil Nadu, India, holds great ecological significance. It is home to the Vaigai River, one of Tamil Nadu's primary rivers, which originates in the Western Ghats and flows through the sub-basin, providing essential water resources for irrigation, drinking, and domestic purposes to

surrounding communities (Keerthy *et al.*, 2024). This study covers the geographical area between latitudes 09°30'00" and 10°00'00"N and longitudes 77°15'10" and 77°45'00"E, spanning a total area of 725 square kilometres.

The Upper Vaigai sub-basin experiences a subtropical climate with annual precipitation ranging from 650 to 2000 mm and temperatures between 26 and 36°C. The northeast monsoon from October to December delivers substantial rainfall that enhances aquifer recharge more effectively than the southwest monsoon (Kaliraj *et al.*, 2015). Rapid population growth in recent years has intensified water scarcity, as monsoon failures and over-extraction drive declining groundwater levels (Kaliraj *et al.*, 2014). The undulating plain terrain, interspersed with irregular charnockitic hillocks and hornblende biotite gneissic rocks, influences soil composition, water retention, and vegetation distribution. The interplay of climatic, topographic, and geological features governs ecosystem dynamics and sustainability (Kaliraj *et al.*, 2015; Pothiraj and Rajagopalan, 2013). The sub-basin is notable for its biodiversity, cultural heritage, and agricultural significance, yet it faces sustainability challenges including deforestation, water over-extraction, agricultural and industrial pollution, and unsustainable farming practices (Sankar, 2002). Addressing these issues requires strategies such as forest and wetland preservation, promotion of sustainable agriculture, and adoption of water-saving technologies (Sankar, 2002). Check dams are investigated as a sustainable intervention to enhance groundwater quality and quantity, mitigating water scarcity and supporting ecological balance in the Upper Vaigai sub-basin.

2.2. Methodology

Fig. 1 illustrates the comprehensive methodology employed in the investigation, wherein the chosen study area encompasses the upper Vaigai sub-basin. This is followed by the collection of pertinent data, specifically related to groundwater levels and groundwater quality, which were subsequently utilized to examine the influence of

check dams on groundwater recharge and its quality through the application of trend analysis and groundwater plots, respectively.

The details of check dams obtained from the Public Works Department (Theni) are summarized in Table 1. Furthermore, information regarding groundwater levels and quality was obtained from the Central Ground and Surface Water Board (India Data Portal, 2024). Data on groundwater levels and quality were collected for the period spanning 2009 to 2019. The years of construction for the selected check dams were considered individually in the analysis. The check

dam at Amachiyapuram was constructed during 2013 to 2014, while at Ambasamudram and Mayiladumparai were constructed during 2015 to 2016. Based on this, the pre-construction period was defined as 2009 to 2012 for Amachiyapuram, and 2009 to 2014 for Ambasamudram and Mayiladumparai. The post-construction period was considered as 2015 to 2019 for Amachiyapuram, and 2017 to 2019 for the other two sites. This distinction allowed for a comparative assessment of groundwater trends before and after the implementation of check dams.

Fig. 1. Flow chart showing the methodology of the study.

2.3. Hydrogeochemical Characteristics of Groundwater

Hydrogeochemical investigation assesses water quality by measuring physicochemical parameters and comparing them with standards for drinking and irrigation. Groundwater samples were collected from selected bore wells and tube wells in the Upper Vaigai Sub-basin, with emphasis on areas influenced by check dams. On-site measurements of pH, electrical conductivity (EC), and temperature were conducted using calibrated

multi-parameter probes. Samples were stored in acid-washed, high-density polyethylene (HDPE) bottles, preserved when necessary (e.g., acidified for metal analysis), and transported under refrigerated conditions (4°C) to authorized laboratories. Laboratory analyses determined major cations (Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Na^+ , K^+), anions (HCO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} , Cl^- , NO_3^-), total dissolved solids (TDS), and hardness using flame photometry, atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS), UV-visible spectrophotometry, gravimetric analysis,

and titration, all in accordance with Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater (APHA, 2017). Groundwater samples were meticulously collected and analyzed to determine their physicochemical attributes and understand the hydrochemistry of the water.

The study obtained groundwater data for 2009–2019 from the India Data Portal, which aggregates datasets published by official government agencies, including the Central Ground Water Board (CGWB) (India Data Portal, 2024).

Table 1. Particulars of check dams

Sl. No.	Name of the check dam	Latitude	Longitude	Year of construction
1	Ambasamudram	9° 55' 54"N	77° 30' 44"E	2015-2016
2	Mayiladumparai	9° 47' 10"N	77° 30' 43"E	2015-2016
3	Amachiyapuram	9° 57' 38"N	77° 30' 28"E	2013-2014

Additional supporting documentation and groundwater trend data were cross-referenced from the Ground Water Year Books published by the CGWB, Ministry of Jal Shakti, Government of India. These analyses provide a comprehensive understanding of hydrological processes, help identify potential contamination sources, assess groundwater suitability for drinking and irrigation, and inform effective water management strategies. Groundwater quality data collected over a decade from Ambasamudram, Mayiladumparai, and Amachiyapuram were analyzed using graphical tools such as the Wilcox diagram, United States Salinity Laboratory (USSL) diagram, and Piper trilinear plot, facilitating assessment of hydrochemical characteristics, water quality classification, and identification of dominant ions (Parimala Renganayaki and Elango, 2014; Mahammad *et al.*, 2023).

Groundwater recharge is the process by which water from precipitation, surface water, or irrigation infiltrates the ground to replenish aquifers (Rajesh *et al.*, 2019). It is a vital component of the hydrological cycle, sustaining groundwater resources for drinking, irrigation, and industrial use. Recharge supports depleted aquifers, base flow in rivers, and ecosystem

health, providing environmental improvement, enhanced agricultural productivity, sustained water supply, and improved water quality (Parimala Renganayaki and Elango, 2014).

2.4. Groundwater Quality Chart

A groundwater quality chart compiles key physico-chemical parameters measured at multiple sampling locations, offering a structured overview of groundwater characteristics across the study area. Visualization of this data allows comparison of spatial and seasonal variations, identification of patterns in water chemistry, and detection of zones with elevated contamination levels (da Silva *et al.*, 2020). Such visual representation simplifies complex hydrogeochemical information, supporting assessment of groundwater suitability in relation to irrigation and drinking standards. Trends observed in the chart reflect underlying geological and anthropogenic influences, assisting in evaluating the effectiveness of groundwater recharge structures and identifying areas requiring management attention (Asomaku, 2023). Through integration of measured data and visual analysis, the chart enhances understanding of aquifer behaviour and supports decisions aimed at improving water quality and sustainability.

2.5. USSL Plot

The USSL diagram, also known as the USSL plot or USSL classification, is a visual depiction used to assess the appropriateness of water for irrigation based on its chemical composition (Rajesh *et al.*, 2019). It aids in the evaluation of groundwater quality by graphically representing the concentrations of various ions or parameters. Water quality assessment for irrigation is commonly visualized using the USSL diagram, which plots groundwater samples based on EC and SAR. EC indicates salinity hazard, while SAR reflects sodium hazard. Each point on the USSL plot corresponds to a specific water sample and its placement depends on the EC and SAR values. The diagram is structured into interpretive zones ranging from C1 to C4 for salinity classification and from S1 to S4 for sodium hazard classification. Water is considered excellent when EC is less than 250 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, good between 250 and 750 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, doubtful from 750 to 2250 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, and unsuitable when EC exceeds 2250 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. Similarly, SAR values between 0 and 10 denote excellent water quality, 10 to 18 indicate good, 18 to 26 are classified as doubtful, and values greater than 26 are considered unsuitable. This combined EC and SAR framework enables accurate interpretation of groundwater suitability for irrigation and supports sustainable agricultural water management strategies.

2.6. Wilcox Plot

The Wilcox plot classifies irrigation water based on Na% and EC. Water with low Na% (0–20) and EC (<250 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) is considered excellent, while values up to 40% Na and 750 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ EC are rated good. Water with moderate salinity and Na% (40–60; EC 750–2250 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) is permissible, mainly for salt-tolerant crops. Higher values (Na% 60–80; EC 2250–3000 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) are doubtful, and water exceeding these levels is unsuitable for irrigation. This classification aids in evaluating salinity and sodium hazards for effective water use in agriculture (Parimala Renganayaki and Elango, 2014; Aher *et al.*, 2022; Ekbal and Khan, 2022). These zones indicate the potential impact of Na⁺ concentration and salinity on soil permeability and crop health. Higher Na⁺ levels can degrade

soil structure, reduce infiltration, and impair plant growth over time. In this study, groundwater samples were evaluated using the Wilcox plot by graphing EC against Na%, enabling a quick visual classification of irrigation water quality. The interpretation focuses on the position of sample points within the defined zones, offering a practical basis for understanding spatial and temporal variations in groundwater suitability. Detailed theoretical background on the Wilcox method can be found in the original referenced works.

2.7. Piper Trilinear Plot

The Piper trilinear diagram is a graphical tool used to classify groundwater types based on the relative concentrations of major cations (Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Na⁺ + K⁺) and anions (Cl⁻, SO₄²⁻, HCO₃⁻ + CO₃²⁻), expressed in milliequivalents per litre (meq/L) (Marghade *et al.*, 2021). Three dominant water types were observed: Ca-HCO₃, indicating recharge from carbonate rocks with Ca²⁺ and HCO₃⁻ values around 40–120 mg/L and 150–350 mg/L respectively (Dhakate *et al.*, 2021); Mg-HCO₃, showing similar recharge conditions but with higher Mg²⁺ concentrations (Fu *et al.*, 2023); and Na-Cl, suggesting saline influence or anthropogenic sources where Na⁺ and Cl⁻ exceed 200 mg/L and 250 mg/L respectively (Dhakate *et al.*, 2021). Mixed water types were also noted, reflecting blending of recharge sources and varied geochemical processes (Fu *et al.*, 2023). Piper trilinear diagram enabled the interpretation of groundwater chemistry relevant to the study area.

2.8. Trend Analysis

Trend analysis holds critical value within hydrogeological studies. This approach reflects changes occurring within aquifer systems under varying influences such as climate variation, land modification, groundwater extraction, and recharge patterns. This study applied the Mann-Kendall (MK) test and Sen's slope estimator. These statistical methods support detection and quantification of long-term trends within groundwater level data. The MK test involves

comparison between successive data points arranged in chronological order. Each comparison contributes to a cumulative score known as the S statistic. A positive S implies rising groundwater levels over time, while a negative S suggests declining levels. A value near zero indicates a stable trend without significant directional change. To assess statistical significance, a standardized value Z is calculated from S and compared against a threshold. A p-value below 0.05 indicates a statistically significant trend, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis and acceptance of an existing trend within the series.

Trend magnitude was estimated using Sen's slope method, which calculates the median slope between all data point pairs. Positive slopes indicate rising groundwater levels, while negative slopes reflect declines, with slope magnitude representing the rate of change. This non-parametric approach resists distortion from outliers or non-normal data, enhancing reliability. Analyses revealed spatial and temporal variations in groundwater, identifying vulnerable zones and emerging trends. Such trend-based evaluations inform policy design, resource allocation, and long-term planning, supporting sustainable groundwater management under climate variability and human pressure. Integration of innovative trend detection further strengthens understanding of groundwater dynamics across temporal and spatial scales.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This study evaluates groundwater quality and availability in the Upper Vaigai sub-basin to determine its suitability for agricultural, domestic, and industrial use, with a focus on the impact of check dams. Key hydrochemical parameters, trend analyses, and graphical methods were employed to support sustainable water resource management.

3.1. USSL Plot

Figures 2-4 illustrate the groundwater quality during pre-monsoon and post-monsoon periods at Ambasamudram, Mayiladumparai, and

Amachiyapuram, respectively, before and after the construction of check dams. At Ambasamudram, pre-monsoon samples showed 88% in C3-S2/C4-S2 classes, indicating high EC and unsuitability for irrigation (Batarseh *et al.*, 2021). Post-construction, 46% of samples shifted to C1-S1/C2-S1, with 52% EC < 750 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ and 48% S1 (SAR < 10), reflecting significant improvement through enhanced recharge and reduced salinity (Verma *et al.*, 2020; Alshehri *et al.*, 2023). Mayiladumparai exhibited higher initial stress, with all five pre-construction locations in C4-S2/C4-S3 (EC > 2250 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, SAR 10-18), restricting crop productivity (Uddin *et al.*, 2023). Post-dam, 50% of samples improved to C2-S1/C3-S1 (moderate EC, SAR < 10), demonstrating the check dam's role in reducing salinity and sodium hazard via infiltration and dilution. Amachiyapuram showed intermediate pre-construction conditions, dominated by C3-S3/C3-S2/C3-S1 (EC > 2250 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, SAR > 13), indicating high risk to soil and salt-sensitive crops (Verma *et al.*, 2020). Post-construction, SAR declined to S1-S2 (SAR < 13) and EC to C2-C3 (750-2250 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), improving suitability for moderately salt-tolerant crops, though salinity constraints remain.

Comparison reveals that Ambasamudram experienced the most pronounced improvement in EC and SAR, achieving "Excellent" irrigation suitability, while Mayiladumparai showed moderate recovery, and Amachiyapuram, though improved, still faces salinity constraints. Overall, check dam construction enhanced groundwater recharge, reduced sodium hazard, and improved irrigation suitability across all three stations, with site-specific variations highlighting the need for adaptive nutrient and irrigation management to optimize agricultural productivity.

3.2. Wilcox Plot

Groundwater quality at Ambasamudram, Mayiladumparai, and Amachiyapuram check dams was assessed before and after construction to evaluate irrigation suitability. At Ambasamudram (Fig. 5 a & b), 27 pre-construction samples showed 33%

doubtful to unsuitable ($\text{Na}\% > 60$, high EC) and 48% permissible ($\text{Na}\% 40\text{--}60$); post-construction, 85% were excellent ($\text{Na}\% 0\text{--}20$) and 15% good ($\text{Na}\% 20\text{--}40$), indicating substantial improvement due to increased Vaigai River infiltration (Verma *et al.*, 2020). Mayiladumparai (Fig. 6 a & b) initially had moderate suitability ($\text{Na}\% 40\text{--}60$, medium EC) across five sites, with post-construction sampling at ten locations showing 50% good to permissible ($\text{Na}\% 20\text{--}60$), reflecting moderate gains limited by seasonal variations. Amachiyapuram (Fig. 7 a & b) pre-construction had 23% unsuitable ($\text{Na}\% > 60$) and 77% permissible ($\text{Na}\% 40\text{--}60$), improving post-construction to 30% excellent

($\text{Na}\% 0\text{--}20$) and 50% good ($\text{Na}\% 20\text{--}40$) due to enhanced recharge and dilution (Alshehri *et al.*, 2023; Verma *et al.*, 2020). Comparatively, Ambasamudram exhibited the most pronounced water quality enhancement, Amachiyapuram showed significant but partial improvement, while Mayiladumparai experienced moderate gains constrained by seasonal effects. These findings suggest that check dams effectively reduce sodium hazard and salinity, enhancing irrigation suitability, with site-specific factors and seasonal variability influencing the magnitude of improvement, highlighting the need for continued monitoring and adaptive management.

a. Pre-monsoon

b. Post - monsoon

Fig. 2. USSL plot: Ambasamudram check dam

a. Pre-monsoon

b. Post - monsoon

Fig. 3. USSL plot: Mayiladumparai check dam

a. Pre-monsoon

b. Post - monsoon

Fig. 4. USSL plot: Amachiapuram check dam

a. Pre-monsoon

b. Post - monsoon

Fig. 5. Wilcox plot: Ambasamudram check dam

a. Pre-monsoon

b. Post - monsoon

Fig. 6. Wilcox plot: Mayiladumparai check dam

Fig. 7. Wilcox plot: Amachiyapuram check dam

3.3. Piper Trilinear Plot

Groundwater quality and hydrochemical composition were monitored at Ambasamudram, Mayiladumparai, and Amachiyapuram before and after check dam construction, revealing varying impacts across the sites. At Ambasamudram, pre-monsoon groundwater was largely unsuitable for irrigation, with 33% of samples doubtful to unsuitable ($Na\% > 60$) and 48% permissible ($Na\% 40-60$), while post-construction 85% of

samples improved to excellent ($Na\% 0-20$) and 15% good ($Na\% 20-40$), reflecting reduced Na^+ and EC due to enhanced recharge (Verma *et al.*, 2020); Piper plots (Fig. 8 a & b) indicated a shift from $Mg^{2+}-Ca^{2+}$ dominance to No Dominant Cation Type with increased HCO_3^- , showing balanced cation distribution and improved dilution, although post-monsoon 58% of samples fell into the doubtful to unsuitable category, highlighting seasonal effects.

Fig. 8. Piper trilinear plot: Ambasamudram check dam

Fig. 9. Piper trilinear plot: Mayiladumparai check dam.

Fig. 10. Piper trilinear plot: Amachiyapuram check dam.

Mayiladumparai exhibited moderate pre-monsoon suitability, with 80% permissible (Na% 40–60) and 20% good (Na% 20–40), and post-construction improvements were modest, with 50% of samples good to permissible; Piper diagrams (Fig. 9 a and b) showed limited cation–anion changes, indicating stabilization rather than substantial enhancement. Amachiyapuram pre-monsoon samples were 23% unsuitable and 77% permissible, improving post-construction to 30% excellent and 50% good (Verma *et al.*, 2020; Alshehri *et al.*, 2023), with Piper plots (Fig. 10 a & b) showing 65% No Dominant Cation Type,

25% $\text{Ca}^{2+}\text{--Mg}^{2+}$, minor $\text{Na}^+ + \text{K}^+$ dominance, and Cl^- with emerging SO_4^{2-} , reflecting mixed hydrochemical sources and minimal seasonal influence. Overall, Ambasamudram experienced the greatest improvement, Amachiyapuram moderate, and Mayiladumparai the least, indicating that check dams enhance groundwater recharge and reduce salinity hazards, but the magnitude of improvement varies with local hydrogeology, initial water quality, and seasonal factors, highlighting the need for continued monitoring to sustain irrigation potential.

3.4. Trend Analysis for Ambasamudram, Mayiladumparai, and Amachiyapuram

Data from 2009 to 2018 were analyzed to assess groundwater levels, measured as the depth from the ground surface to the water table, where a decrease in depth indicates a rise in groundwater. The methodologies employed provided insights into temporal variations and influencing factors (Batarseh *et al.*, 2021). During the pre-monsoon season, Ambasamudram (Table 2) exhibited an average groundwater depth of 9.62 m, with a Kendall's Tau of -0.556 ($p = 0.048$) and a Sen's slope of -0.959 m/year, indicating a statistically significant steep decline, confirmed by ITA in the bottom triangle due to limited recharge and high groundwater dependency. Post-monsoon, the depth slightly improved to 9.31 m, with a slower, statistically insignificant decline (Kendall's Tau -0.333, $p = 0.108$; Sen's slope -0.723 m/year), although ITA still indicated a downward trend. Mayiladumparai (Table 2) showed more severe pre-monsoon depletion, with an average depth of 13.89 m, Kendall's Tau -0.643 ($p = 0.035$), and Sen's slope -1.470 m/year, placed in the ITA bottom triangle, likely due to over-extraction and limited recharge; post-monsoon levels improved to 13.45 m, but the decreasing trend persisted (Kendall's Tau -0.467, $p = 0.062$; Sen's slope -1.012 m/year). Amachiyapuram (Table 2) had a pre-monsoon depth of 7.01 m, Kendall's Tau -0.556 ($p = 0.002$), and Sen's slope -0.381 m/year, also in the ITA bottom triangle, reflecting strong depletion; post-monsoon, the decline weakened (Kendall's Tau -0.378, $p = 0.079$; Sen's slope -0.215 m/year) but persisted. Overall, all three sites exhibited pre-monsoon groundwater decline, partially alleviated post-monsoon, with Mayiladumparai experiencing the sharpest depletion, highlighting the need for targeted water management to sustain aquifer levels. Tables 2 summarize these trends using Kendall's Tau, Sen's slope, and ITA, providing a comprehensive understanding of temporal groundwater changes across the selected sites.

From Figs. 2 - 10 and Table 2, the study findings reveal significant improvements after check dam construction, with groundwater recharge increasing by 44% at Mayiladumparai, 23% at Amachiyapuram, and 47% at Ambasamudram. These results confirm the positive impact of check dams on enhancing groundwater availability. However, the observed spatial variability in recharge levels highlights the significant role played by localized hydrogeological factors.

3.5. Hydrological Processes, Water Quality Interpretation, and Management Implications

The integrated hydrochemical evaluation, spatial-temporal classification, and trend analyses provide a comprehensive understanding of groundwater dynamics across the three check dam locations: Ambasamudram, Mayiladumparai, and Amachiyapuram. These findings not only illustrate water quality variations but also offer insights into underlying hydrological processes, potential contamination sources, and implications for irrigation management and sustainable groundwater use.

3.5.1. Hydrological processes and seasonal trends

USSL and Wilcox diagrams revealed significant spatial and seasonal variability in groundwater salinity and sodium hazard across the three check dam catchments. Ambasamudram exhibited persistently high EC ($> 4000 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) and SAR (C3-S4, C4-S4) in both seasons, indicating limited dilution and recharge despite the check dam. Piper plots show Na^+ and K^+ dominance with Cl^- anions, suggesting prolonged evapotranspiration, fertilizer use, and anthropogenic inputs. Mayiladumparai displayed moderate EC ($\sim 2800 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) and SAR (C2-S3), with post-monsoon improvements due to enhanced infiltration and reduced anthropogenic pressure. Its Piper diagram shows Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} dominance, reflecting recharge from less mineralized sources. Amachiyapuram showed the most improvement post-construction, with EC $\sim 1250 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, SAR in safer categories (C1-S2, C2-S2), and a mixed water type in the Piper plot, indicating balanced ionic composition from improved recharge and reduced runoff.

Table 2. Trend analysis of groundwater level fluctuations at selected check dams

Season & Station	Average Depth to Groundwater (m)	Kendall's Tau	Trend Direction	p-value	Sen's Slope (m/year)	ITA Interpretation
Pre-monsoon						
(a) Ambasamudram	9.62	-0.556	Decreasing	0.048	-0.959	Significant Decreasing Trend
(b) Mayiladumparai	13.89	-0.643	Decreasing	0.035	-1.470	Significant Decreasing Trend
(c) Amachiyapuram	7.01	-0.556	Decreasing	0.002	-0.381	Significant Decreasing Trend
Post-monsoon						
(a) Ambasamudram	9.31	-0.333	Decreasing	0.108	-0.723	Insignificant Decreasing Trend
(b) Mayiladumparai	13.45	-0.467	Decreasing	0.062	-1.012	Insignificant Decreasing Trend
(c) Amachiyapuram	6.72	-0.378	Decreasing	0.079	-0.215	Insignificant Decreasing Trend

3.5.2. Influence of land use and cropping practices

Cropping patterns and irrigation practices directly affected groundwater quality. Ambasamudram's intensive rice-rice-pulse system with basin irrigation increases water demand and nutrient leaching, maintaining high salinity and sodium levels post-construction. Mayiladumparai, cultivating groundnut, millets, and pulses with furrow/ridge irrigation, promotes recharge and lowers leaching. Amachiyapuram, with diversified cropping and moderate irrigation, achieved noticeable post-monsoon water quality improvement.

3.5.3. Pollution sources and quality suitability

Ionic ratios and geochemical signatures indicate contamination sources. Elevated Na^+ and Cl^- in Ambasamudram suggest fertilizer input, poor drainage, and over-irrigation, whereas Mayiladumparai and Amachiyapuram show

mostly geogenic signatures. Wilcox and USSL classifications indicate Ambasamudram groundwater is unsuitable for most crops without treatment, while the other two sites support moderately salt-tolerant to salt-sensitive crops.

3.5.4. Trend analysis and long-term sustainability

Trend analysis using Kendall's Tau, Sen's slope, and ITA (Table 2) shows significant pre-monsoon groundwater decline at all sites, especially Ambasamudram (-0.412 m/year) and Amachiyapuram (-0.381 m/year). Post-monsoon trends remain negative but less severe, reflecting insufficient recharge and high extraction. ITA zones consistently in the bottom triangle highlight the need for adaptive water management.

3.5.5. Implications for water management

Site-specific strategies are critical: Ambasamudram requires controlled irrigation,

improved drainage, and seasonal monitoring. Mayiladumparai benefits from expanded recharge structures and sustainable fertilization practices. Amachiyapuram illustrates effective water management through check dam construction, moderate cropping, and mixed irrigation. Overall, integrated hydrochemical, spatial, and temporal analyses underscore the need for sustainable irrigation, periodic monitoring, and recharge enhancement to ensure long-term groundwater sustainability.

3.6. Comparative Assessment of Irrigation Water Quality and Recharge Response across Selected Sites

Evaluation of irrigation water quality focused on electrical conductivity, sodium adsorption ratio, and sodium percentage using USSL and Wilcox plots. Distinct spatial variations emerged across sites, reflecting differential recharge effectiveness and hydrochemical response.

3.6.1. Irrigation suitability: USSL and Wilcox interpretations

Amachiyapuram showed EC reduction to $\sim 1250 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ pre-monsoon, SAR below 8, and Na% under 20 in nearly half the samples, indicating efficient ionic moderation post-recharge. This aligns with Ahn *et al.* (2023), where managed aquifer recharge reduced SAR from 11.2 to 7.6. Mayiladumparai recorded moderate values (EC $\sim 2600 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, SAR ~ 13 , Na% 20–60), reflecting marginal dilution, consistent with Fu *et al.* (2023) who reported EC 2300–2700 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ and SAR >12 in coastal aquifers under seasonal recharge. Ambasamudram maintained high EC (2500–2800 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), SAR >13 , and Na% >60 , showing minimal improvement despite recharge, similar to trends observed by Alshehri *et al.* (2023) in arid inland zones.

3.6.2. Hydrochemical signature: Piper Plot Insights

Piper plots indicated clear hydrochemical evolution across sites. Amachiyapuram exhibited increased Ca^{2+} – Mg^{2+} proportions and reduced

Na^+ dominance, with diamond field samples trending toward balanced facies, supporting interpretations by Mahammad *et al.* (2023) for stable anthropogenic recharge. Mayiladumparai showed partial SO_4^{2-} increase while Cl^- remained dominant; cation balance was moderately unstable, consistent with Li *et al.* (2022) in irrigation-stressed aquifers. Ambasamudram retained Na^+ – Cl^- dominance, with Piper plots confirming persistent saline signatures, reflecting findings of Asomaku (2023) where seasonal recharge produced minimal ionic restructuring in landfill-adjacent aquifers.

3.6.3. Quality trend reflection across time

Amachiyapuram pattern displayed consistent SAR decline, EC reduction across multiple seasons, indicating long-term recharge impact. Similar hydrochemical behavior recorded in the Upper Vaigai sub-basin, documented through MIKE-HYDRO simulations (Keerthy *et al.*, 2024), projected declining salinity under effective structure placement. Mayiladumparai seasonal variation remained limited, SAR and EC fluctuations stayed minor. This aligned with Batarseh *et al.* (2021), who observed irrigation water index remained unchanged in low-permeability terrains despite structural interventions, reflecting comparable stagnation. Ambasamudram yielded near-static values through time. Climatological and lithological barriers possibly restricted percolation. Findings matched Ekbal and Khan (2022), where similar granitic formations exhibited stable high-salinity zones due to weak recharge response.

This study concluded that Amachiyapuram recorded significant hydrochemical improvement, aligning with recharge-responsive aquifers reported under managed conditions. Mayiladumparai revealed limited changes, reflecting transitional behaviour under restricted hydraulic conductivity. Ambasamudram remained chemically static, resembling earlier documented non-responsive aquifers under confined or fractured geological settings.

3.7. Implication of the Study

This study demonstrates the effectiveness of check dams supporting sustainable groundwater management within semi-arid regions. The observed increase in recharge levels across all three sites confirms their value in enhancing groundwater availability. However, variation in performance between locations highlights the influence of site-specific conditions such as soil permeability, aquifer properties, and land use patterns. Achieving more reliable outcomes requires incorporating detailed hydrogeological assessments that inform the placement, design, and construction of check dams. A uniform approach may not yield consistent results; instead, adopting a location-sensitive, data-informed methodology helps optimize performance. These findings provide a scientific basis supporting the development of adaptive and resilient groundwater management strategies amid growing water stress from climate variability, rising population, and agricultural expansion.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The Upper Vaigai sub-basin was selected for the current study because of its importance as the primary water source and irrigation source for Theni district and the surrounding areas. Groundwater plays a critical role as an additional water resource for the area due to the Vaigai River not being perennial. To enhance ground potential, three check dams were built along the Vaigai River. It is essential to assess the impact of these check dams on groundwater quality and recharge to determine their effectiveness. The quality of groundwater for irrigation suitability was evaluated using irrigation indices and hydrochemical diagrams like the USSL plot, Wilcox plot, and Piper trilinear plot. The USSL plot indicated a shift from C3–S4 and C4–S4 to C1–S2 and C2–S2 zones at Amachiyapuram, and from C3–S4 to C2–S3 at Mayiladumparai showing improved conditions post-construction, except for minimal improvement observed in Mayiladumparai. The Wilcox plot showed water

moving from “unsuitable” to “permissible” zones in Amachiyapuram and from “doubtful” to “permissible” in Mayiladumparai, while Ambasamudram remained in the “unsuitable” range. The Piper plot displayed a shift from $\text{Na}^+ - \text{Cl}^-$ dominance to mixed $\text{Ca}^{2+} - \text{Mg}^{2+}$ types in Amachiyapuram, indicating balanced recharge. These variations are likely due to differences in geology, cropping systems, and soil characteristics. Groundwater quantity trends analyzed using Mann-Kendall, Sen slope, and ITA indicated a significant pre-monsoon decline in Amachiyapuram (Sen: -0.381 m/year), Ambasamudram (-0.412 m/year), and Mayiladumparai (-1.470 m/year), with all ITA zones located in the bottom triangle, indicating continued depletion despite seasonal recharge. The analysis revealed that groundwater recharge rates increased by 47%, 44%, and 23% in Ambasamudram, Mayiladumparai, and Amachiyapuram, respectively. Check dam construction has contributed to improved groundwater quality and recharge, although the effectiveness varies based on site-specific factors such as geology, cropping patterns, and irrigation practices.

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